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A Non-Parametric Analysis of the Alignment between Net-Zero Indicators and Sustainability Reporting Practices: The Case of Türkiye's Basic Metal Industry

Sıfır Atık Göstergeleri ve Sürdürülebilirlik Raporlaması Uygulamaları İlişkisine Yönelik Non-Parametrik Bir Analiz: Türkiye Ana Metal Endüstrisinden Örnekler

ABSTRACT

This study examines the association between net-zero indicators and sustainability reporting practices among entities in the Turkish Basic Metal Industry. Using publicly available data listed on the Public Disclosure Platform (KAP) as of October 29, 2025, the analysis encompasses 28 entities, and evaluates the data set containing sustainability principles compliance levels, and the related net-zero indicators; net-zero certification, waste recycling rate, annual waste generation, net-zero targets and net-zero training activities. Given the small sample size and the non-normal distribution of the data, non-parametric statistical methods; Fisher's Exact, Mann-Whitney U, Pearson Chi-Square, Kruskal Wallis H Tests, and Spearman's rank correlation were employed in the study. The empirical findings of the study reveal that holding a net zero certificate does not necessarily increase the likelihood of compliance with sustainability principles. Conversely, it mostly remains formal or symbolic. That result reflects a notable collaboration gap and lack of integration between net-zero indicators and sustainability practices This study contributes to the sustainability reporting literature by providing empirical evidence from an emerging economy context and offering insights into the environmental sustainability drivers of the basic metal industry in Türkiye.

Keywords: Net-zero, Net-zero practices, Sustainability, Sustainability reporting

ÖZET

Bu çalışma, Türkiye'de faaliyet gösteren ana metal sanayi firmalarının sıfır atık göstergeleri ile sürdürülebilirlik raporlaması uygulamaları arasındaki ilişkiyi incelemektedir. Çalışmada, Kamuyu Aydınlatma Platformu (KAP) üzerinden erişime açık veriler kullanılmış olup, analiz kapsamında 28 firma yer almaktadır. Çalışmada değerlendirilen çevresel açıklama göstergeleri arasında sıfır atık sertifikasyonu, atık geri dönüşüm performansı, sürdürülebilirlik raporlarının varlığı, rapor uyum düzeyi, atık azaltma hedefleri ve atık yönetimi ile ilgili eğitim faaliyetleri bulunmaktadır. Veri setinin küçüklüğü ve normal dağılım göstermemesi nedeniyle, değişkenler arasındaki ilişkileri incelemek için non-parametrik istatistiksel yöntemler kullanılmıştır; bunlar arasında Fisher Kesinlik Testi, Mann-Whitney U Testi ve Spearman sıra korelasyonu yer almaktadır. Araştırmanın ampirik bulguları, sıfır atık sertifikasına sahip olmanın sürdürülebilirlik ilkelerine uyum düzeyini artırmadığını, aksine, bu sertifikasyonların büyük ölçüde sembolik nitelikte kaldığını göstermektedir. Çalışma, non-parametrik istatistiksel analizleri sürdürülebilirlik açıklama kalitesinin değerlendirilmesinde uygulayarak sürdürülebilirlik ve çevresel muhasebe literatürüne katkı sağlamaktadır. Ayrıca, gelişmekte olan bir ekonomi bağlamında ana metal sanayinin çevresel yönetim dinamiklerine dair ampirik kanıt sunmaktadır.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Sıfır atık, Sıfır atık uygulamaları, Sürdürülebilirlik, Sürdürülebilirlik raporlaması.

1. INTRODUCTION

Corporate sustainability responsibility has rapidly become fundamental initiative that determine not only entities' economic performance but also their ability to assess and manage environmental, social and governance aspects. Corporate sustainability responsibility encompasses two key dimensions: net-zero practices and sustainability reporting disclosures. Sustainability (ESG) reporting is globally defined as an *“organization’s practice of publicly disclosing an organization’s most significant economic, environmental, and/or social impacts, and hence its contributions; positive or negative towards the goal of sustainable development”* (GRI, 2025). In this context, net-zero or carbon neutral constitutes a resource and waste management approach based on circularity that promotes sustainability as widespread concept. It represents a core element of the environmental aspect of ESG reporting. Moreover, net-zero practices serve as one of the most critical indicators of environmental compliance with sustainability principles. Accordingly, net-zero has been a defining frame for climate action since the Paris Agreement. Given the growing global emphasis on circular economies, the transition to net-zero systems and practices has become a central focus of corporate sustainability strategies. Thus, the collaboration between net-zero commitments and sustainability reporting practices is required.

Net-zero practices play a significant role in ESG reporting. The environmental aspect (E) in ESG reporting focuses on environmental stewardship, and demonstrates the performance of the entities' efforts towards climate change, reducing pollution and waste, and taking advantage of environmental opportunities. These areas are referred to the principal focal points of net-zero practices (PwC, 2020). Particularly in industrial sectors, environmental practices such as net-zero practices, waste management and energy efficiency are critical for ensuring regulatory compliance and meeting stakeholder expectations (KPMG, 2022). In this context, net-zero indicators and ESG reporting have emerged as two key mechanisms that document environmental performance and enhance transparency. Entities operating in the basic metal industry in Türkiye represent a critical area of study due to the high energy and raw material intensity of their production processes, as well as the potential environmental impacts of their waste generation. However, empirical research examining the relationship between net-zero practices and sustainability reporting in this industry remains limited. Most prior studies focus on high-income countries or large-scale entities, leaving a notable gap regarding industrial entities in emerging economies. This study aims to investigate the relationship between net-zero indicators (e.g., net-zero certification status, net-zero targets, net-zero trainings, waste generation, and waste recycling rates) and sustainability reporting practices among Turkish basic metal entities, using non-parametric statistical methods. The dataset comprises information from 28 entities publicly disclosed on the Public Disclosure Platform (KAP), and relationships among variables were examined using Fisher's Exact Test, Mann-Whitney U Test, Pearson Chi-Square Test, Kruskal Wallis H Test, and Spearman's rank correlation.

The primary motivation of the study is to determine how well net-zero indicators are integrated and reflected in the sustainability reporting in practice. Empirical studies based on the research area are very limited that points out the research gap in Turkish context. This study is conducted on comprehensive empirical research. Therefore, the study's primary contribution lies in empirically demonstrating that certification and sustainability reporting function as interconnected components of corporate environmental sustainability. Furthermore, the study provides a methodological contribution for evaluating sustainability disclosures in small sample and non-normally distributed datasets by applying non-parametric analysis. As a result, the research purposes novel insights into environmental sustainability practices in the Turkish basic metal industry and contributes to the literature on sustainability reporting in an emerging economy context.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

This study first reviews the current literature converging net-zero and sustainability reporting indicators, disclosures and practices within context of Türkiye, then examines the relevant international literature. Finally, the study articulates the specific research gap, particularly in relation to the current study's focus.

2.1. Research on Current Literature within in Context of Türkiye

The crucial role of sustainability indicators, practices and, disclosures thus sustainability reporting in achieving goals of corporate sustainability responsibility have been demonstrated by researchers across different countries over the last decade. In parallel, recent studies on sustainability reporting in Türkiye have provided valuable insights into the current practices and limitations of sustainability disclosures. For instance, Gökçen and Kayacan (2024) suggest that net-zero reporting in Türkiye is largely symbolic, serving as an element of corporate reputation rather than a systematically measured environmental performance

indicator. Their study on automotive companies listed in BIST Sustainability 25 Index also emphasizes the association between net-zero disclosures and sustainability practices according to the disclosure requirements of GRI 306 Waste Standard. Complementing these perspective, Barik & Deste (2024) provides solid evidence about how regulatory frameworks and international agreements like Paris Climate Agreement shape sustainability reporting practices through a content analysis. The study underscores the need for integrating measurable net-zero indicators into sustainability disclosures in their study on white goods sector in Türkiye. Their analysis reveals that these disclosures often focus on policy compliance and reputational considerations rather than providing standardized, quantifiable performance indicators. Furthermore, Korga & Aslanoğlu (2024) have provided a comprehensive analysis of how corporations prioritize sustainability indicators in the scope of their sustainability reporting practices. The authors emphasize that while corporations listed in BIST Sustainability Index often report on a broad range of environmental, social, and governance (ESG) indicators, the relative importance and performance measurement of each indicator are not always clear or standardized. This highlights a critical gap in sustainability reporting frameworks, as the effectiveness and comparability of sustainability disclosures largely depend on identifying which indicators truly reflect organizations' sustainability performance. Their findings further reinforce the need for more structured and quantifiable approaches to sustainability reporting aligning with the current study's aim of assessing how net-zero indicators and disclosures are integrated into sustainability reporting practices, and the extent to which they are reflected in sustainability reporting performance of Türkiye's basic metal industry.

Savsar (2023) has provided valuable information about environmental sustainability reporting practices of the banks listed in BIST Sustainability Index with particular attention to net-zero and waste management indicators. The study's findings reveal that while banks often mention general environmental policies and energy efficiency initiatives, specific data on net-zero or waste recycling is limited and inconsistently reported. This is primarily referred to a gap in the integration of measurable environmental indicators, particularly regarding net-zero, within sustainability reports.

Cengiz (2022) emphasizes that corporations often lack systematic approaches to disclosing environmental information in their reporting practices. Her study on Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) supports the argument that sustainability reporting in Türkiye remains largely compliance-oriented rather than performance-oriented. The findings further reveal the need for more comprehensive frameworks linking net-zero indicators with sustainability disclosure practices. Collectively, the previous studies indicate that sustainability reporting in Türkiye increasingly addresses environmental initiatives, net-zero targets, and waste management practices, yet disclosures remain largely descriptive, selective, and symbolic, with limited standardized or quantifiable metrics. Sector-specific evidence from different kind of sectors such as automotive, white goods, and banking, etc. shows that net-zero and sustainability reporting is driven more by regulatory compliance and reputational concerns than measurable environmental performance. Critically, the integration and prioritization of net-zero and other waste related indicators remain inconsistent, highlighting a persistent gap in structured, performance-oriented sustainability reporting frameworks. This gap reinforces the need for empirical investigation into how net-zero indicators are integrated and reflected in the sustainability reporting performance of Türkiye's basic metal industry, which constitutes the primary motivation of the current study.

2.2. Research on the Recent International Literature

Recent studies in international literature refers to the crucial role and increasing prominence of net-zero commitments across various industries, yet emphasizes that their operationalization and reporting quality remain in the infancy stages. Siswanti and Wijayanti (2025) examine sustainability disclosures of energy companies in Indonesia during 2020–2022, emphasizing that while disclosure levels have improved over time, most companies provide qualitative rather than quantitative information. The study suggests that net-zero commitments are still in infancy or early stages of implementation. Building on the findings of Siswanti & Wijayanti (2025) in the energy sector, D'Silva (2025) extends the analysis to the aviation industry, highlighting similar challenges regarding transparency and reporting quality. D'Silva (2025) refers to the strong correlation between carbon management practices, transparency levels, and governance structures. According to his research, "carbon management," "transparency & reporting" and "alternative fuels" are the most frequently discussed sustainability themes in aviation industry. The findings of the research emphasize that leading global airlines vary widely in their sustainability reporting approaches and there are still significant reporting gaps regarding strong net-zero pledges, transparency and quality of sustainability reporting as a whole.

Liu et al. (2024) demonstrated that banks affiliated with Net-Zero Banking Alliance disclose significantly higher levels of environmental information than their non-member counterparts, implying that net-zero commitments might act as a catalyst for improved ESG performance. Di Vaio et al. (2024) analyze the linkage between carbon accounting outputs and integrated reporting based on a systematic literature review containing 433 academic articles in the field of sustainability accounting. The study considers carbon accounting and integrated reporting as an essential mechanism through which net-zero commitments translate into improved sustainability indicators, including ESG scores. Bag (2024) shows that implementation and adoption of sustainable net-zero economy have a positive impact on financial, environmental and social performance of corporations by using variance-based structural equation model in chemical manufacturing industries of South Africa. Crocco et al. (2024) show that companies exhibit significant variation in their sustainability reporting themes, with topic modelling revealing how net-zero transition risk and sectoral exposure influence disclosure practices. Sharaf-Addin (2024) reveals that sustainability reporting aligned with the GHG Protocol Framework plays a pivotal role in facilitating the transition towards net-zero carbon emissions, particularly in carbon intensive industries, and emphasizes reporting quality as a key determinant of effective decarbonization. Collectively, these studies suggest that net-zero commitments, when combined with transparent reporting mechanisms, might enhance the quality and credibility of sustainability indicators, thus sustainability reporting across sectors.

Asif et al. (2023) proposes a Sustainable Business Model (SBM) focusing on environmental impact of the food, beverage and tobacco companies. Based on the research comparing 252 food, beverage and tobacco companies, they identify the integration between environmental sustainability factors and Osterwaider's Business Model by focusing on delivering net-zero value to customers. According to the research, net-zero is considered as an environmental sustainability factor. Followingly, Yadav et al. (2023) use real-world datasets from conference of parties (COP) meetings in their study. They highlight that the achievement of net-zero emission by sustainable development goals (SDGs) requires high level of integration of lean and green as well as adoption of digital technologies.

Fankhouser et al. (2022) identifies seven key attributes to net-zero in their study. These attributions emphasize the need for environmental and social integrity. The study shows that, net-zero must be aligned with sustainable development goals which involve net-zero transition, social-ecological sustainability and broad economic opportunities.

Hale et al. (2021) reveal that although so many corporations have adopted net-zero emission targets, only a few corporations could meet the criteria of robust net-zero targets, operationally. Based on the review of over 4000 countries, the research points out the need of setting robust net-zero targets into motion regarding the more effective climate-action in the concept of sustainability. Because, operationalization of net-zero is still in its infancy although it is a widespread concept. Foundational studies by Fankhouser et al. (2022) and Hale et al. (2021) further underscore that operationalizing net-zero remains nascent despite widespread adoption, requiring alignment with social & ecological sustainability and robust climate-action goals.

Taken together, these studies indicate while net-zero commitments and indicators are increasingly prominent and widely reported across different industries, their operationalization, alignment and integration with robust sustainability reporting practices remain in its early stages, focusing on the need for stronger reporting practices towards net-zero.

3. RESEARCH METHODS

3.1. Research Design and Sampling

This study examines the association between net-zero reporting indicators and sustainability reporting practices among entities operating within the basic metal industry in Turkey. According to the most recent data published by the Turkish Statistical Institute (TURKSTAT) in 2024 (<https://data.tuik.gov.tr/Bulten/Index?p=Atik-Istatistikleri-2024-54134>), the highest proportion of industrial waste within the manufacturing sector is generated by the manufacture of basic metals and fabricated metal products (11.705.716 ton), which constituted the primary determinant for selecting the study sample. The research sample comprises 28 entities that were listed on the Public Disclosure Platform (KAP) as of October 29, 2025 (<https://kap.org.tr/tr/Sektorler>), with data publicly accessible. Descriptive information pertaining to the study sample are summarized in the table below:

Table 1. Descriptive Information about the Variables

Code	Net-Zero Certificate	Waste ^a Recycling Rate	Annual Waste Generation	Net-Zero Training	Net-Zero Target	Sustainability Principles Compliance Level
AYES	Not available	Low	Absent	Present	Present	Weak
BMSTL	Available	High	Present	Present	Present	Yes
BMSCH	Not available	Low	Absent	Absent	Present	Partly
BRSAN	Available	high	Present	Present	Present	Yes
BURCE	Not available	Low	Absent	Present	Present	Weak
BURVA	Not available	Low	Absent	Present	Present	Irrelevant
CELHA	Available	Low	Absent	Present	Present	Weak
CEMAS	Not available	Low	Absent	Present	Present	Weak
CEMTS	Not available	Low	Absent	Present	Present	Yes
CUSAN	Available	Low	Absent	Present	Present	Partly
DMSAS	Available	Low	Present	Present	Present	Yes
DOFER	Not available	Low	Absent	Absent	Absent	Irrelevant
DOKTA	Not available	high	Present	Present	Present	Yes
ERBOS	Not available	Low	Absent	Absent	Present	Partly
ERCB	Not available	High	Present	Present	Present	Yes
EREGL	Available	High	Present	Present	Present	Partly
ISDMR	Available	High	Present	Present	Present	Partly
IZMDC	Available	High	Present	Present	Present	Partly
KRDMA, KRDMB, KRDMD	Available	Low	Present	Present	Present	Yes
TCKRC	Not available	Low	Absent	Absent	Present	Weak
KCAER	Available	High	Absent	Present	Present	Yes
KOCMT	Available	Low	Absent	Absent	Present	Weak
MEGMT	Available	High	Present	Present	Present	Yes
OZYSR	Available	Low	Present	Present	Present	Weak
PNLSN	Available	Low	Present	Present	Present	Partly
SARKY	Not available	Low	Present	Present	Present	Partly
TUCLK	Not available	Low	Absent	Present	Present	Partly
YKSLN	Not available	Low	Absent	Absent	Present	Weak

a. If waste recycling rate is $\leq 0,50$; low, $>0,50$; high

Data on the net-zero reporting indicators of the entities included in the Table-1 particularly net-zero certification, waste recycling rate, waste generation, net-zero training, and net-zero targets were primarily retrieved from the entities' sustainability reports. For entities that did not publish a formal sustainability report, the relevant information was obtained from the entities' official websites, particularly within the "Investor Relations" and "Sustainability" sections. These sections provide detailed information on environmental policies, energy management practices, waste management strategies, circular economy initiatives, and net-zero roadmaps. The evaluation of the entities' sustainability reporting compliance levels was conducted based on the Sustainability Principles Compliance Reports issued by the Capital Market Board of Turkey (CMB). These reports were used as the benchmark to determine the degree to which each entity aligns with nationally required sustainability compliance principles.

All of the variables in the data collected were first subjected to normality tests to determine whether the assumption of normal distribution was met. The results indicated that the dataset did not conform to a normal distribution; therefore, non-parametric statistical methods were employed for analysis. Specifically, the study applied:

- Fisher's Exact Test to examine associations between the binary categorical variables,
- Mann-Whitney U Test for comparisons between two independent groups on ordinal or non-normally distributed continuous variables,
- Kruskal-Wallis H Test for comparisons across more than two groups, and
- Spearman's Rho Correlation to assess the strength and direction of monotonic relationships between ordinal variables.

These non-parametric methods were chosen to ensure the robustness and validity of the analyses given the distributional characteristics of the data.

3.2. Tests of Normality

To assess whether the sample conformed to a normal distribution, the Kolmogorov–Smirnov and Shapiro–Wilk normality tests were employed, and the corresponding p-values were evaluated. The results of the normality assessments for the research sample are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Tests of Normality

	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
Waste recycling rate	,294	28	,000	,762	28	,000
Net-zero certification	,337	28	,000	,639	28	,000
Sustainability report	,355	28	,000	,637	28	,000
Sustainability principles compliance level	,247	28	,000	,804	28	,000
Net-zero target	,539	28	,000	,188	28	,000
Net-zero training	,482	28	,000	,508	28	,000
Annual waste generation	,337	28	,000	,639	28	,000

The significance (p) values obtained from both tests were below the 0.001 significance threshold. These results indicate a statistically significant deviation from a normal distribution across all variables. Therefore, the dataset does not satisfy the assumption of normality, and the use of non-parametric statistical methods is warranted for subsequent analyses.

3.3. Non-Parametric Tests

3.3.1. The Assessment of the Association between Net-Zero Reporting Indicators and Sustainability Principles Compliance Levels

Firstly, a Mann–Whitney U test was employed to determine whether entities with net-zero certification differ from non-certified entities in terms of their sustainability principles compliance levels. But, in the sample of the study almost all entities (27 out of 28) had already established a net-zero target, while only one entity had not. Due to this extreme imbalance, the variable didn't produce two analytically meaningful groups, and therefore no inferential statistical test (such as the Mann–Whitney U test) could be conducted. As the non-target group comprised a single observation, the distributional assumptions required for nonparametric group comparison were not met. Consequently, net-zero target adoption was reported descriptively rather than tested statistically, and the variable was excluded from inferential analyses.

The analysis revealed that entities with a net-zero certification ($n = 14$) demonstrated higher sustainability reporting compliance on average (Mean Rank = 16.61) compared to entities without such certification (Mean Rank = 12.39). This pattern suggests a tendency for certified entities to exhibit more advanced alignment with sustainability reporting requirements. Despite this descriptive difference, the test did not yield statistically significant results. The Mann–Whitney U statistic was $U = 68.50$, accompanied by a Z-value of -1.420 and a two-tailed significance level of $p = 0.156$, exceeding the conventional $\alpha = .05$ threshold. The exact significance value ($p = 0.178$) corroborates the absence of a statistically reliable difference between the groups. Accordingly, the evidence does not support the assertion that net-zero certification is associated with higher sustainability reporting compliance levels within this sample. The results are shown below:

Table 3. Ranks of Sustainability Principles Compliance Level and Net-Zero Certification

	net_zero_certification	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks
sus_princip_comp_level	absent	14	12,39	173,50
	present	14	16,61	232,50
	Total	28		

Table 4. Test Statistics

	sus_rep_comp_level
Mann-Whitney U	68,500
Wilcoxon W	173,500
Z	-1,420
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	,156
Exact Sig. [2*(1-tailed Sig.)]	,178 ^b

Secondly, the study tested whether net-zero training affects sustainability principles compliance level (H_0 : there is no difference in sustainability principles compliance level between participants who adopted net-zero training and those who didn't ; H_1 : there is a difference in sustainability principles compliance level between participants who adopted net-zero training and those who didn't) using the Mann Whitney U test, appropriate for the ordinal dependent variable and small sample size ($n = 28$). The findings of the test are presented in Table 5 and 6.

Table 5. Ranks of Sustainability Principles Compliance Level and Net-Zero Training

	net_zero_training	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks
sus_princip_comp_level	absent	6	8,83	53,00
	present	22	16,05	353,00
	Total	28		

Table 6. Test Statistics

	sus_princip_comp_level
Mann-Whitney U	32,000
Wilcoxon W	53,000
Z	-1,994
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	,046
Exact Sig. [2*(1-tailed Sig.)]	,059 ^b

The asymptotic two-tailed p-value suggested a borderline significant difference between the groups ($U = 32.000$, $Z = -1.994$, $p = 0.046$). However, considering the small sample size, the Exact two-tailed significance ($p = 0.059$) provides a more reliable assessment. Accordingly, there is no statistically significant difference in sustainability principles compliance level between participants who received net-zero training and those who did not.

Thirdly, A Kruskal Wallis H Test was employed to determine whether waste recycling rates differed according to the level of sustainability principles compliance level among entities in the basic metal industry. The test reflected a statistically significant difference between groups ($H(3) = 13.62$, $p = 0.003$). Mean rank values indicated that entities with a high sustainability principles compliance level (“Yes”) had the highest waste recycling rates, followed by “Partly,” while “Weak” and “Irrelevant” groups showed lower rates. The findings of the Kruskal Wallis H tests are presented in Table 7, and 8.

Table 7. Ranks of Sustainability Principles Compliance Level and Waste Recycling Rate

	sus_princip_comp_level	N	Mean Rank
waste_recycling_rate	weak	8	8,81
	irrelevant	2	7,50
	partly	9	14,06
	yes	9	21,56
	Total	28	

Table 8. Test Statistics

	waste_recycling_rate
Chi-Square	13,620
df	3
Asymp. Sig.	,003

In addition, a Spearman’s rank order correlation was performed to assess the relationship between sustainability principles report compliance levels and waste recycling rates. The analysis revealed a strong, positive, and significant correlation ($p = 0.690$), indicating that entities with higher sustainability compliance levels tend to achieve higher recycling rates. These results collectively suggest that adherence to sustainability principles is associated with improved waste management performance.

Table 9. Correlations between Sustainability Principles Compliance Levels and Waste Recycling Rates

		sus_rep_princip_level	waste_recycling_rate
Spearman's rho	sus_princip_comp_level	Correlation Coefficient	1,000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	,690**
	waste_recycling_rate	N	28
		Correlation Coefficient	,690**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	,000
		N	28

3.3.2. The Assessment of the Association among Net-Zero Reporting Indicators

To examine whether net-zero reporting practices tend to co-occur within entities, additional non-parametric association tests were employed exclusively among the four net-zero indicators. This section of the study seeks to address the following questions:

- i. Do entities holding net-zero certifications exhibit higher recycling rates?
- ii. Do entities holding net-zero certifications engage in more net-zero related training activities?
- iii. Do entities holding net-zero certifications demonstrate clearer annual waste generation disclosures?
- iv. Do entities adopting net-zero related training activities achieve higher recycling rates?

Given the categorical structure of the first three research questions and the small sample size, Fisher's exact test was applied to assess the associations. For the fourth research question, which involves comparing waste recycling rate distributions between two independent groups, the Mann–Whitney U test was employed due to its suitability for non-normally distributed data.

Firstly, the association between the Net-Zero Certification (available/not available) and the waste recycling rate (high/low) was initially assessed using the Pearson Chi-Square test, which suggested a significant relationship ($p = 0.043$) at the 5% significance level. However, as half of the cells had expected frequencies below 5, the Chi-Square results may not be reliable. Therefore, Fisher's Exact Test, which is more appropriate for small expected frequencies, was applied. Hypotheses for Fisher's Exact test for the first research question is the followings:

H_0 : There is no statistically significant association between the presence of a net-zero certification (available/not available) and the level of waste recycling rate (high/low); the two variables are independent.

H_1 : There is a statistically significant association between the presence of a net-zero certification (available/not available) and the level of waste recycling rate (high/low); the two variables are not independent.

The Fisher's Exact Test result ($p = 0.103 > 0.05$) has indicated that there is no statistically significant association between holding a net-zero certification and the level of recycling rate. This suggests that holding a net-zero certificate does not necessarily correspond to a high ($> 0,50$) or low ($\leq 0,50$) waste recycling rate. The results are presented in Table 10 below:

Table 10. Chi-Square Tests^c

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	4,094 ^a	1	,043	,103	,052
Continuity Correction ^b	2,620	1	,106		
Likelihood Ratio	4,273	1	,039	,103	,052
Fisher's Exact Test				,103	,052
N of Valid Cases	28				

a. 2 cells (50,0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 4,50.

b. Computed only for a 2x2 table

c. For 2x2 crosstabulation, exact results are provided instead of Monte Carlo results.

Secondly, the association between net-zero certification and net-zero training activities was examined using a 2×2 cross-tabulation and Fisher's Exact Test due to small expected cell counts. The cross-tabulation indicated:

i. Among net-zero certified entities, 7 entities had adopted net-zero related training activities and 7 entities hadn't adopted net-zero related training activities.

ii. Among non-certified entities, 2 entities had adopted net-zero related trainings and 12 entities hadn't adopted net-zero related training activities.

Although the Pearson Chi-Square test suggested a marginal association ($\chi^2 = 4.094$, $df = 1$, $p = .043$), the Fisher's Exact Test more appropriate given that 50% of cells had expected counts below 5 produced a two-sided p-value of .103. This result indicates that the association between certification status and the presence of net-zero related trainings not statistically significant at the conventional $\alpha = .05$ threshold. In other words, having a net-zero certification does not reliably predict whether an entity adopts net-zero training, although a descriptive pattern suggests that net-zero certified entities are somewhat more likely to have adopted net-zero related training more than non-certified entities. The results are presented in Table 11 below:

Table 11. Chi-Square Tests^c

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	4,094 ^a	1	,043	,103	,052
Continuity Correction ^b	2,620	1	,106		
Likelihood Ratio	4,273	1	,039	,103	,052
Fisher's Exact Test				,103	,052
N of Valid Cases	28				

a. 2 cells (50,0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 4,50.

b. Computed only for a 2x2 table

c. For 2x2 crosstabulation, exact results are provided instead of Monte Carlo results.

Thirdly, the association between net-zero certification and annual waste generation was examined using a 2×2 cross-tabulation and Fisher's Exact Test. The cross-tabulation showed:

- i. Among net-zero certified entities, 10 entities reported annual waste generation while 4 entities didn't.
- ii. Among non-certified entities, only 3 entities reported annual waste generation while 11 entities didn't.

Fisher's Exact Test indicated a statistically significant association between net-zero certification status and annual waste generation reporting (two-sided $p = .021$). Entities with net-zero certificate were more likely to report their annual waste generation than non-certified entities, suggesting that holding or obtaining a net-zero certification is associated with greater transparency or compliance in annual waste reporting practices. The Pearson Chi-Square test confirmed this finding ($\chi^2 = 7.036$, $df = 1$, $p = .008$), and the minimum expected cell count was above 5, validating the appropriateness of the test. The results are presented in Table 12 below:

Table 12. Chi-Square Tests^c

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	7,036 ^a	1	,008	,021	,011
Continuity Correction ^b	5,169	1	,023		
Likelihood Ratio	7,373	1	,007	,021	,011
Fisher's Exact Test				,021	,011
N of Valid Cases	28				

a. 0 cells (0,0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 6,50.

b. Computed only for a 2x2 table

c. For 2x2 crosstabulation, exact results are provided instead of Monte Carlo results.

Finally, A Mann–Whitney U test was employed to examine whether firms that adopt net-zero related training activities differ in their waste recycling rates compared to entities that don't adopt. The analysis revealed:

- i. Entities that adopt net-zero training ($n = 21$) had a higher mean rank in waste recycling rate (Mean Rank = 15.17) than entities without net-zero training ($n = 5$; Mean Rank = 6.50).

The Mann–Whitney U test indicated a statistically significant difference between the two groups ($U = 17.50$, $Z = -2.398$, two-tailed $p = 0.016$). The exact significance value corroborated this result ($p = 0.019$), confirming that entities adopted net-zero related trainings exhibit significantly higher recycling rates than entities without such training. The results are presented in Table 13, and 14 below:

Table 13. Ranks of Mann Whitney U Test

	net_zero_training	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks
waste_recycling_rate	absent	5	6,50	32,50
	present	21	15,17	318,50
	Total	26		

Table 14. Test Statistics^a

	waste_recycling_rate
Mann-Whitney U	17,500
Wilcoxon W	32,500
Z	-2,398
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	,016
Exact Sig. [2*(1-tailed Sig.)]	,019 ^b

a. Grouping Variable: net_zero_training

b. Not corrected for ties.

3.4. Results

In the first stage of the research, the association between net-Zero reporting indicators and sustainability principles compliance levels were analysed. Given the non-normal distribution of the variables Mann Whitney U, Kruskal Wallis H tests and Spearman's rank order correlation were employed in the analysis. The findings are summarized in Table 15:

Table 15. The Associations between Net-Zero Reporting Indicators and Sustainability Principles Compliance Level

Variables Independent & Dependent	Non-parametric test used	test	Significance (p) value	The Results
Net-zero certification	Sustainability principles compliance level	Mann Whitney U	$p = 0.178$	$P = 0.178 > 0.05$ (statistically no significant difference)
Net-zero training	Sustainability principles compliance level	Mann Whitney U	$p = 0.059$	$P = 0.059 > 0.05$ (statistically no significant difference)
Waste recycling rate	Sustainability principles compliance level	Kruskal Wallis H Test and Spearman's Rank Order Correlation	$p = 0.003$	$P = 0.059 < 0.05$ (statistically significant difference)

The analysis examined whether sustainability principles compliance levels differed across entities with varying net-zero reporting indicators (net-zero certification, net-zero training, and waste recycling rates). The empirical findings of the research indicate that net-zero certification status does not significantly influence sustainability principles compliance levels. The Mann–Whitney U test revealed no statistically significant difference between certified and non-certified entities ($p = 0.178 > 0.05$). Similarly, net-zero training practices were not associated with differences in compliance levels, as the Mann Whitney U Test again showed a non-significant result ($p = 0.059 > 0.05$). These findings suggest that the mere presence of certification or adoption of net-zero related training initiatives does not necessarily translate into higher adherence to sustainability principles. In contrast, a statistically significant association emerged for waste recycling rate. Results from the Kruskal Wallis H Test demonstrated that entities with different waste recycling rates exhibited significantly different sustainability compliance levels ($p = 0.003 < 0.05$). This result was supported by Spearman’s rank-order correlation, indicating a meaningful monotonic relationship between recycling rate and compliance performance. Thus, unlike certification or training, tangible operational practices, specifically waste recycling performance appear to be a stronger determinant of sustainability principles compliance within the entities operate in basic metal industry in Türkiye.

In the second stage of the research, the study explored whether entities’ net-zero reporting indicators exhibited internal coherence by examining pairwise associations among four indicators: net-zero certification, net-zero training, waste recycling rate, and annual waste generation., Fisher’s Exact Test was used for binary & binary combinations, while the Mann Whitney U test was employed for interrelationships between binary and ordinal variables. Table 16 presents a summary of the all findings.

Table 16. The Interrelationships among Net-Zero Reporting Indicators

Variable combinations	Tests used	Significance (p) value	Results
Net-zero certification and waste recycling rate	Fisher’s Exact Test	P=0.103	P=0.103 > 0.05 (no significant association)
Net-zero certification and net-zero training	Fisher’s Exact Test	P=0.103	P=0.103 > 0.05 (no significant association)
Net-zero certification and annual waste generation	Fisher’s Exact Test	P=0.021	P=0.021 < 0.05 (significant association)
Waste recycling rate and net-zero training	Mann-Whitney U	P=0.019	P=0.019 < 0.05 (significant association)

Depending on the measurement structure of each variable pair as shown in Table 16, Fisher’s Exact Test was used for binary & binary combinations while the Mann Whitney U test was employed for interrelationships between binary and ordinal variables.

The findings reveal that net-zero certification is not significantly associated with waste recycling rates ($p = 0.103 > 0.05$) nor with net-zero training practices ($p = 0.103 > 0.05$). These results suggest that holding a net-zero certification does not necessarily coincide with operational recycling performance or with the implementation of employee-oriented net-zero training programs. However, the analysis identified a statistically significant association between net-zero certification and annual waste generation ($p = 0.021 < 0.05$). This indicates that certified entities differ from non-certified entities in terms of the amount of waste they generate annually, implying that certification may be linked to broader structural or operational characteristics influencing waste output.

Furthermore, the waste recycling rate was found to be significantly associated with net-zero training ($p = 0.019 < 0.05$). This result suggests that entities adopting employee-oriented net-zero training tend to achieve higher or more consistent recycling performance, indicating that internal capacity-building initiatives may translate into more concrete environmental outcomes.

Taken together, these findings have provided supplementary insights into the coherence and internal alignment of entities’ net-zero reporting practices. While net-zero certification alone does not co-occur consistently with most operational indicators, training practices and waste generation patterns appear to play a more substantial role in shaping the coherence of entities' net-zero efforts.

4. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

This study examined the associations between net-zero reporting indicators and entities’ sustainability principles compliance levels, and further examined the internal coherence among different net-zero reporting indicators. Employing a series of non-parametric statistical tests, including the Fisher’s Exact Test, Mann Whitney U Test, Pearson Chi-Square Test, Kruskal Wallis H Test, and Spearman’s rank order correlation, the empirical findings reveal several significant insights regarding the nature and depth of organizational net-zero engagement in the basic metal industry in Türkiye.

Regarding the first phase of the analysis, the findings reveal that neither net-zero certification nor net-zero training activities generate statistically significant differences in sustainability principles compliance levels. These results imply that formal or symbolic commitments; such as certifications and internal awareness efforts might not be sufficient to elevate sustainability compliance on their own. Instead, they may reflect an early or superficial stage of net-zero adoption, without yet translating into measurable improvements in sustainability performance.

In contrast, waste recycling performance demonstrated a statistically significant influence on sustainability principles compliance levels, emphasizing the central role of operational behaviour in driving substantive sustainability outcomes. This suggests that performance-based indicators rather than commitment-based indicators serve as more accurate indicators of an entity's genuine alignment with sustainability compliance principles.

The second stage of the analysis further demonstrated that net-zero indicators do not always develop in parallel. While certification displayed no significant association with recycling rates or training initiatives, it was significantly associated with annual waste generation, indicating potential structural or industry-specific differences between certified and non-certified organizations. Above all, the significant association between recycling performance and training activities suggests that internal capacity building efforts might translate into more effective environmental practices when implemented meaningfully.

All of the findings emphasize the need for organizations to move beyond symbolic or administrative commitments, and to strengthen the operational dimensions of sustainability reporting and net-zero practices. It is evident that net-zero practices are still in their early stages and require further development. The results underscore the importance of aligning net-zero initiatives with measurable environmental performance indicators to achieve meaningful progress. Moreover, the empirical results yield several implications for policymakers, regulators, and standard setting bodies. Regarding the results, the need for a transition from symbolic, certification-driven approaches to more performance-oriented sustainability frameworks is prominent. Given that certifications do not consistently reflect actual environmental outcomes, policymakers should strengthen performance-oriented reporting requirements rather than relying on certifications or declarations of net-zero commitments. However, setting-up requirements for performance-oriented net-zero reporting, solely is not likely to be enough. These reporting requirements must be supported by proper protocols and standards for ensuring a transparent and accurate net-zero reporting process. In addition, the positive association between net-zero training and operational outcomes suggests that embedding mandatory or incentive-based net-zero training components within regulatory frameworks could enhance overall sustainability performance across industries. From a managerial perspective, the findings underscore the significance of prioritizing operational improvements over reputational gains linked to net-zero certifications. Enhancing waste management processes, employing data-driven monitoring systems, and designing net-zero training programs that are closely integrated with daily operations appear to be critical for achieving substantive environmental progress.

Eventually, the study reflects how well net-zero indicators fit in sustainability reporting practices in fact based on a comprehensive non-parametric analysis. The empirical results show the related deficiencies and discrepancies in net-zero reporting in Turkish basic metal industry based on solid evidence. In addition to the recommendations stated above, according to KPMG (2025) twelve quality criteria might be taken into consideration to ensure collaborated net-zero reporting with sustainability reporting matters. These criteria developed by climate disclosure experts of KPMG are as follows:

1) *Board responsibility*: This criterion requires the board of the directors of the company to take net-zero climate response and change seriously. It emphasizes the importance of overseeing the company's response and holds the board of the company responsible, ultimately.

2) *Chair of CEO's message*: This criterion involves climate change matters or risks into CEO's messages in company's annual financial reports or integrated reports. According to this criterion, acknowledgement of climate change matters or risks by top of the company constitutes a strong signal for investors of the company.

3) *Acknowledge financial risk*: This criterion requires the acceptance of climate change as a potential financial risk of the company in its financial or integrated report, clearly.

- 4) *Clear reporting*: This criterion requires to add separate section about climate change to the company's financial or integrated report and risks including a stand-alone climate risk (TCFD) report.
- 5) *Physical and transitional risk*: This criterion considers both physical and transitional risks arisen from climate change and net-zero transition as integrated components of reporting.
- 6) *Scenario analysis*: This criterion requires to include a scenario analysis to provide a forward-looking view for investors and other stakeholders about company's potential resilience to climate change or risks.
- 7) *Range of scenarios and clear timeline*: This criterion requires to include risk analyses preferably two or more than two in line with different global warming scenarios to provide a better understanding of the company's climate risk profile regarding investors and other stakeholders.
- 8) *Reputable scenario source*: This criterion requires companies to make reliable and robust analyses by using reputable sources.
- 9) *Science-aligned targets*: This criterion requires to set net-zero and climate change targets, reasonably. According to these criteria, a company should state its ambition to achieve net zero carbon emission in line with global deadlines.
- 10) *Clear decarbonization strategy*: This criterion requires to state out the company's ways or strategy to achieve its decarbonization targets.
- 11) *Transparency on progress*: This criterion requires to provide a completely transparent reports by a company regarding investors' confidence. For this purpose, a company should clearly report that it is able to meet its carbon reduction targets or it has some challenges and dilemmas that might hinder the progress.
- 12) *Internal carbon price*: This criterion requires to report an internal carbon price or a shadow price to reflect a sign that the company is well prepared to climate-related risks.

These twelve criteria set a good guideline to develop the collaboration between net-zero practices and sustainability reporting. They make easier to manage climate-related risks including net-zero indicators, thus achieve net-zero targets.

5. LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY AND FUTURE RESEARCH

Despite its contributions, this study has several limitations. Therefore, the interpretation of these findings must account for the study's limitations, including sample size constraints, the cross-sectional nature of the data, and measurement simplifications. Future research should expand the scope of investigation through larger and more diverse samples, longitudinal research designs, and more granular indicators to better capture the complexities of net-zero practices and their organizational drivers.

REFERENCES

- Asif, M.S., Lau, H., Nakandala, D. & Hurriyet, H. (2023). Paving the way net-zero: identifying environmental sustainability factors for business model innovation through carbon disclosure project data. *Frontiers in Sustainable Food Systems*, 7, 1-21. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fsufs.2023.1214490>
- Bag, S. (2024). From resources to sustainability: A practice-based view of net zero economy implementation in small and medium business to business firms. *Benchmarking: An International Journal*, 31(6), 1876-1894. <https://doi.org/10.1108/BIJ.01.2023-0056>
- Barik, E. & Deste, M. (2024). Tedarik zinciri yönetiminde paris iklim anlaşmasının etkilerinin sürdürülebilirlik raporları üzerinden analizi: beyaz eşya sektöründen örnekler. *Süleyman Demirel Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü Dergisi*, 1(48), 339-359.
- Cengiz, S. (2025). Çevre muhasebesi, çevresel sürdürülebilirlik ve ÇED raporlarının incelenmesi. *Manisa Celal Bayar Üniversitesi İ.İ.B.F Yönetim ve Ekonomi Dergisi*, 32(1), 147-167.
- Crocco, E., Broccardo, L., Atofaysan, H. & Agarwal, R. (2024). Sustainability reporting in carbon-intensive industries: insights from a cross-sector machine learning approach. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 33, 7201-7215. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bse.3850>
- D'Silva, M.N. (2025). Towards net zero: analyzing sustainability reports of global airlines. *International Journal of Environmental Sciences*, 11(5), 781-813. <https://doi.org/10.64252/e8t51d12>

- Di Vaio, A., Zaffar, A., Chhabra, M. & Balsalobre-Lorente, D. (2024). Carbon accounting and integrated reporting for net-zero business models towards sustainable development: A systematic literature review. *Business Strategy and Environment*, 33, 7216-7240. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bse.3863>
- Fankhouser S., Smith, S.M., Allen, M., Axelsson, K., Hale, T., Hepburn, C., Kendall, J.M., Khosla, R., Lezaun, J., Mitchell-Larson, E., Oberstenier, M., Rajamani, L., Rickaby, R., Seddon, N. & Wetzler, T. (2022). The meaning of net-zero and how to get it right. *Nature Climate Change*, 12, 15-21. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41558-021-01245-w>
- Hale, T., Smith, S.M., Black, R., Cullen, K., Fay, B. and Mahmoud, L.S. (2021). Assessing the rapidly emerging landscape of net-zero targets. *Climate Policy*, 22(1), 18-29. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14693062.2021.2013155>
- Gökçen, B.A. ve Kayacan, A. (2024). BİST sürdürülebilirlik 25 endeksinde yer alan otomotiv şirketlerinin çevresel sürdürülebilirlik performanslarının içerik analizi ile değerlendirilmesi. *Marmara Üniversitesi Öneri Dergisi*, 19(61), 77-94.
- GRI. (2025). *The value of sustainability reporting and the GRI standards*. <https://www.globalreporting.org/media/jzylyu3ek/the-value-of-sustainability-reporting-and-the-gri-standards.pdf>
- Korga, S. & Aslanoğlu, S. (2024). Sürdürülebilirlik raporlamasında sürdürülebilirlik göstergelerinin önem düzeylerinin belirlenmesi. *Muhasebe ve Finansman Dergisi*, 102, 1-18.
- KPMG. (2022). *Global survey of sustainability reporting: big shifts, small steps*. <https://assets.kpmg.com/content/dam/kpmg/se/pdf/komm/2022/Global-Survey-of-Sustainability-Reporting-2022.pdf>
- KPMG. (2025). *Towards net zero: how the world's largest companies report on climate risk and net zero transition*. <https://assets.kpmg.com/content/dam/kpmgsites/bh/pdf/2024/09/towards-net-zero.pdf.coredownload.pdf>
- Liu, X., Cai, S., Wang, Y. & Sun, Y. (2024). A comparative study of environmental information disclosure between banks in net-zero banking alliance and China, *Technological Forecasting & Social Change*, 202, 1-13. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2024.123324>
- PwC. (2020). *Net zero & ESG at PwC*. <https://www.pwc.com/m1/en/about-us/pwc-supply-chain-guidance-net-zero-and-esg.pdf>
- Savsar, C. (2023). Bankalarda çevresel sürdürülebilirlik raporlaması: BİST sürdürülebilirlik endeksinde yer alan bankalarda bir araştırma. *Malatya Turgut Özal Üniversitesi İşletme ve Yönetim Bilimleri Dergisi*, 4(2), 244-264.
- Siswanti, T. & Wijayanti, D. (2025). The role of energy companies in achieve net zero emissions in Indonesia based on sustainability disclosures period 2020-2022. *Jurnal Bisnis & Akuntansi Unsuraya*, 10(1), 27-42. <https://doi.org/10.35968/jbau.v10i1.1426>
- Yadav, S., Samadhiya, A., Kumar, A., Majumdar, A., Garze-Reyes, J.A. & Luthra, S. (2023). Achieving the sustainable development goals through net zero emissions: innovation-driven strategies for transitioning from incremental to radical lean, green and digital technologies. *Resources, Conversation & Recycling*, 197, 1-19. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2023.107094>